

Exploring Information Seeking of Rural Older Adults During the COVID-19 Pandemic

Brady D. Lund and Jinxuan Ma

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Abstract

Purpose. This study investigates the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the types and sources of information sought by older adults along with their motivations in the Midwestern United States.

Design. Interviews were conducted with 30 older adults residing in rural communities around the Midwestern United States during late-summer (July/August) 2020, using a protocol based on Dervin's Sense-Making approach. The resulting data was analyzed using standard content analysis procedures, guided by the theoretical framework based on Dervin's Sense Making and Williamson's Ecological Model of Information Behavior. Implications of COVID-19 for the normative behaviors described in these models is discussed.

Findings. Findings show that older adults were concerned primarily with health and political information during this period, but that this information was not necessarily sought only to address an informational need, but also to satisfy the need to maintain social and emotional connections in coping with isolation and loneliness. Sources of information that allowed for social interaction with people were favored. Wider personal networks (community members) were strained by the social distancing measures and closures. These findings have theoretical and practical implications for considering the impact of social restrictions on information seeking behaviors of older adults in a time of crisis.

Originality. This study is the first, known to the authors, that applied the two adopted theoretical frameworks to explore information seeking behaviors of older adults during the COVID-19 pandemic.

As the COVID-19 pandemic has posed life-threatening health risks to the public with older adults at highest level of vulnerability, face-to-face communication is less viable as a means to acquire information and severe outbreaks have left many older adults largely confined to their homes. Simultaneously, these individuals' need for reliable information have reached unparalleled levels and multifarious mis- and disinformation has proliferated all forms of media. These situations may have coalesced to form a sense of information crisis, where vital information needs are left unfulfilled (Xie et al., 2020a; Xie et al., 2020b). A lack of quality information and (mis- and dis-) information overload may impact awareness of people's world and their decision-making processes. This, in turn, could result in uninformed, even harmful, decisions that impact people's mental, cognitive, and physical health, their financial and social well-being, and a lack of trust/confidence in political and societal authorities (Norris, 2001; Thompson, 2007).

The purpose of this study is to investigate how rural older adults in the Midwestern United States have made sense of their information environments amid the COVID-19 pandemic, utilizing Dervin's Sense-Making approach in conjunction with an ecological theory of information behavior proposed by Kirsty Williamson (1997; 1998). This approach focuses on identifying where the pandemic has introduced barriers or gaps in rural older adults' daily information seeking activities and understanding how individuals' motivations influence their information seeking behaviors during this time. Identification of these barriers and gaps is key to alleviating unsatisfied information needs through improved information access and support.

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted significant gaps in our understanding of information behavior of older adults in crises. The fundamental research problem that underpins this study is *how have unknown factors surrounding a life-threatening public health crisis*

impacted the sources and types of information that older adults have sought. As Wilson (2000) suggests, information behavior—the information that an individual consumes and how they consume it—may influence other behaviors and beliefs that an individual holds. It is most likely that the pandemic has introduced a substantial shift in the motives and ways that individuals interact, seek, and use information. Individuals' responses to the pandemic—whether to go out in public, wear a mask, and engage in hygienic activities—are potential life-or-death decisions, particularly among older adults, one of the most vulnerable populations. Furthermore, the older adult population is examined infrequently in information behavior research (Julien, Pecoskie, & Reed, 2011). A better understanding of this populations' information behavior will not only make a significant, novel contribution to the body of literature and library practice but knowing specifically about how their information behaviors have shifted during the pandemic has ramifications for natural disaster and other crisis research as well.

Research Questions

To address this research problem, the following overarching research question and four sub-questions were developed:

- How have rural older adults sought to satisfy their information needs in the evolving COVID-19 pandemic landscape?
 - What types of information needs have emerged?
 - What role has the pandemic along with other contextualized (both personal and environmental) factors/influences played for these needs?
 - From what information sources have they sought to address these needs?
 - Have their information needs been satisfied during this period?

Literature Review

Information behavior of older adults

The information use behavior of older adults has been studied in various contexts over the past several decades. Williamson (1999) suggested that the most common uses of information for older adults include for decision-making purposes, such as health, financial, and political information, to connect socially with others, to plan for future events (e.g., vacations or funeral) and to stay current with events occurring in the world. Williamson suggested that the specific uses of information and where this information is acquired is contingent on personal and environmental factors including institutions (e.g., nursing facilities, social services, libraries), mass media, social networks (e.g., friends, family), personal values, lifestyle, socio-economic status, employment status, and personal characteristics. Subsequent researchers proposed additional information uses among older adults, such as to support life reflection and sustain memory (i.e., searching for information about past life experiences) and for religious worship purposes (e.g., reading the bible) (Campbell et al. 2016; Komatsu et al. 2018; Palsdottir, 2012).

Much of the existing information research related to older adults has occurred within the contexts where a large sample of these individuals is easy to find: nursing facilities. However, recruiting participants from nursing facilities may prove problematic for information research, given that less than 10% of adults age 65+ reside in these facilities (meaning that this sample is not representative of the “typical” older adult) (West et al. 2014), and the nature of living in close proximity to peers under the supervision of nurses and aids is likely to affect the information behaviors of older adults in ways that are distinct from older adults that reside independently (Palsdottir, 2012; Pettigrew, 2000).

While the ubiquitous Internet connectivity and rapid technology advancements have helped to abate the digital divide to an extent, there is still a significant gap in the amount,

relevance, and quality of information produced and accessible for older adults compared to other populations in the United States (Padilla-Gongora et al. 2017; Williamson 1998). As noted longitudinally by a collection of interdisciplinary researchers, older adults tend to be “laggard” or “late” adopters of new technologies using the diffusion terminology of Everett Rogers (Caceres & Chaparro 2019; Ferro et al. 2010; Gilly & Zeithaml 1985; Gonzalez, Ramirez, & Viadel 2012; Rogers 1986; Selwyn 2004; Vicente & Lopez 2006). This challenge is exacerbated by the fact that, historically, very little information has been created relevant to the information needs and uses of older adults (Baker 2004; Hales-Mabry 1993). While older adults have been adopting newer technologies, like social media, at faster rates than ever before, they still lag well behind the general (younger adult) population (Leist, 2013; Yang et al., 2016; Zhao & Zhang, 2017). This has left this population reliant on information sources that may be more restrictive (e.g., close family, friends, or television stations) and less reliable. This may have particularly important implications during the COVID-19 pandemic, where access to certain information resources (e.g., community members) was further restricted by social distancing and isolation guidelines.

Existing information behavior studies of older adults were largely conducted in limited contexts. For example, many studies of this population utilized the context of assisted living centers, as it was easy to acquire a large number of participants simultaneously. Other studies focused on independent-living older adults, but only those living in moderate-to-large urban centers, as these were the types of cities where most research universities are located. This means that the rural context is often overlooked. Those studies that do examine the information behaviors of rural older adults almost unilaterally focused on health-related behaviors (Agyemang-Duah et al., 2020; Potter, Allen, & Roberto, 2019; Song et al., 2019; Wilyman,

2017). This is especially true during the COVID-19 pandemic, where few existing studies of older adults' information behavior focus on COVID-specific behavior (Lachlan et al., 2021; Parial et al., 2021; Skarpa & Garoufallou, 2021; Xie et al., 2020c). This study intendeds to expand upon the limited past investigations to examine a range of rural older adults' information behaviors during the era of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Context factors and information behavior

The influence of contextual factors on and in information seeking behaviors has been documented in many recent studies. Agarwal, Xu, and Poo (2011) demonstrated the role of context in source use by workers. Savolainen (2017) discusses how contexts surrounding the emergence of information need driven the manifestation of information seeking behavior. Al-Samarrie, Eldenfria, and Dawoud (2017) examined how different personality traits influences information behavior. Several studies have also looked at how context factors impact health information behaviors of medical patients (Graffigna et al., 2017; Park, Oh, & You, 2020; Walker et al., 2017). These studies all illustrate an important influence of context on how information behaviors manifest, one that has traditionally been overlooking in research. In examining context of information behaviors in this study (the experiences of independently-living older adults in rural communities during the COVID-19 pandemic), it contributes to this growing body of literature.

Studies of information sources during public health crises

Several studies have analyzed information sources and needs during past pandemics. Wong and Sam (2010) analyzed information behavior among adults in Malaysia during the 2009 H1N1 (swine flu) pandemic. The most commonly utilized information sources among this population were newspapers, television, and family. This finding was compelling in light of

Salman, Choy, Mahmud, and Latif's (2013) identification that, by 2012, diffusion of Internet in Malaysia was nearly 100%, meaning that the use of these sources was a matter of preference or completeness more so than access. Wong and Sam (2010) did identify significant differences in source preference based on ethnicity. The researchers also noted that information about prevention and treatment of H1N1 was the most highly needed/valued. Majid and Rahmat (2013) also examined information behavior during the H1N1 pandemic, in their case using individuals living in Singapore as the population. Respondents in this study were asked to indicate how frequently they used a variety of information source to inform themselves about the pandemic. While all respondents indicated that they used some online resources, these were referenced less frequently than human and print and media sources. In fact, the top five sources consulted were television, newspapers, radio, friends, and family.

Sharma, Yadav, Yadav, and Ferdinand (2017) highlight the emerging significance of an information source within their study of the Zika virus pandemic. The researchers raised serious concerns about Facebook as a source of information, finding that misleading or inaccurate posts were, on average, much more popular than reliable posts. This is certainly not a one-off case. Misinformation is frequently found to be rampant on social media platforms (Allcott, Gentzkow, & Yu, 2019; Mian & Khan, 2020; Pennycook, McPhetres, Zhang, Lu, & Rand, 2020). The rapid and widespread diffusion of misinformation on social media can be particularly harmful for populations with low or insufficient information literacy skills (Khan & Idris, 2019).

Studying people's information seeking behaviors amid the COVID-19 has become an urgent research topic in the latest LIS literature (Ali et al., 2020; Kelly, Goke, McCall, & Dowell, 2020; Li & Zheng, 2020; Moreno, Fuentes-Lara, & Navarro, 2020; Superio, 2020; Zimmerman, 2021). While some of these studies focus on older adults, only a handful to date

have focused on older adults from a non-health-specific perspective. For example, Reisdorf et al. (2021) pointed out that older adults utilized conservative news media as an information source more frequently than younger adults, while younger adults used virtually all other types of information sources more frequently. Chu, Garza, Gerstoff, and Hoppmann (2020) found that older adults spent longer time seeking information. El Skarpa and Garoufallou (2021) examined the information sources consulted by different age groups, noting that older adults sought information more commonly from television and less frequently from the Internet relative to other age groups. These empirical studies, by and large, have been atheoretical with the aim of specific aspects of information behaviors (most commonly, sources of information). By expanding the phenomena to be studied (the information seeking process, types of information needs, sources, contexts) and employing a theoretical approach, the present study aims to further our understanding of the information behavior of rural older adults during the COVID-19 pandemic era.

Theoretical Framework for this Study

It is the position of the researchers in this study that a brand new theory of rural older adults' pandemic information behaviors may not be necessary. Instead, there are existing theories we believe can be adapted to investigate this behavior. In the moment, it can seem like the COVID-19 pandemic is a "once-in-a-lifetime," unique event, but, in reality, there are events that emulate the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic that occur frequently: some event that changes what the immediate information needs of individuals are, what sources are available, and how this information is sought (e.g., ecological disasters, other pandemics, emergency health and financial situations). What is really needed to describe information behavior during this pandemic period, then, is a theory that considers emergent, contextualized gaps in information,

like with Brenda Dervin's Sense-Making theory. In conjunction with Sense Making, which provides a framework of the information seeking process, we use Kirsty Williamson's Ecological Model to inform the specific ontology we utilize to describe types of information needs and sources and environmental influences on individuals' information behavior throughout the Sense-Making process. The following section details the significance of each theory and how they align to form the framework for this study.

Sense-Making Approach

Sense-Making as a concept has existed for many decades and been used in diverse contexts (Dervin, 1983). However, in relation to information behavior studies, the greatest contributions have been from the work of Brenda Dervin, a noted scholar from the discipline of communication studies. Dervin (1977) noted that conceptualizations of communication were likely to be beneficial for understanding the information needs of information seekers. Dervin's Sense Making (1977; 1983; 1998) has been referred to as a theory of information behavior, however it is intended as not only a theory but also a methodology for examining how individuals "make sense" of a problem or the world around them. Information is viewed as being reliant on the human user in order to have meaning, with negotiations concerning thought, beliefs, values, emotions, memories, information gaps, information sources, and situations/context informing the effect information has on an individual. The Sense-Making approach focuses on information behavior as experienced by the user, rather than as observed by a researcher. Dervin's Sense Making was a significant contributor to the shift toward user-centered approaches to information behavior, which inspired the largest body of research within this field during the last decades of the 1900s and the first few decades of the 2000s (Dervin, 1977; 1983; 1998; Savolainen, 1993).

Grounded in phenomenological perspectives (understanding of experience and conscious reasoning), Dervin's Sense Making examines the individual from the perspective of the gaps in understanding in which they interact, with situational factors (an individual's background and habits), contexts (power dynamics, culture), information sources, (internal and external) communicative exchanges and activity shape bridges for these gaps (Dervin, 1998). These "bridges" are personal constructs, so the only way for a researcher to really understand them is by reflecting the information needs and patterns of interaction and exchange as the individual understands them (subjectively).

The methods employed in this study are guided by Dervin's situation-gap-use, or situation-gap-outcome, concepts. Sense Making occurs at the intersection of these three points (the existing situation, the presentation of a gap, the outcome that emerges from bridging the gap). As noted by Naumer, Fisher, and Dervin (2008, pp. 3-4), interview questions in Sense-Making studies are designed to identify situations, gaps, bridges, and outcomes as perceived by the individual, asking questions like "what issue were you dealing with?" and "what prevented you from better understanding the situation?" Following this design, a complex picture of contexts, types of information needed, and sources and understanding of information, may be constructed.

Ecological Model

The Ecological Model of Information Behavior emerged from Kirsty Williamson's (1995) doctoral research at the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology, "Older adults: Information, communication and telecommunications." Incidental information acquisition is defined based on Wilson's argument that "people find information unexpectedly as they engaged in other activities, with information acquisition becoming an incidental concomitant"

(Williamson, 2005, p. 128). Williamson is not the only research to conceptualize incidental information acquisition—this is a major component of Savolainen's (1995) *everyday life information seeking*, though not directly named as incidental information acquisition. However, captured in Williamson's model is the idea that the incidental acquisition of information is influenced to varying degrees by various actors in the individual's information ecology.

In Williamson's Ecological Model, the individual is considered to be at the center of a series of concentric circles. These circles represent sources of information and they affect they have on the information acquisition of the individual. The two closest circles to the individual—personal networks and media are said to be limited sources of incidental information acquisition (i.e., information sharing is frequently, intentionally, and overtly occurring). Sources that are institutional, or the structures that are beyond personal networks and media are said to be frequent sources of incidental information acquisition. These structures are a product of variables in the individual's interplay with their ecology/environment, such as lifestyle, social and cultural values, socio-economic circumstances, work situation, personal/biological characteristics, affective/spiritual influences, and physical environment (Williamson, 2005, p. 129); this has alternately been described by Williamson (1998, p. 35) in an early article as “values, lifestyles, physical environments, personal characteristics, and socio-economic circumstances.”

A critical observation in Williamson's studies involving this model was that, in everyday life information seeking among older adults, family and friends (or extended family), are the greatest sources of information for the older adult. In their review of Williamson's work and that of related studies, Williamson, Schauder, and Bow (2000) conclude that “in all studies, regardless of the age groups involved, interpersonal sources take precedence over media sources

(particularly newspapers, television and radio), with institutional sources such as local councils and libraries less frequently used” (para. 10).

There is considerable overlap between the theoretical perspective of Dervin and the Ecological Theories associated with Williamson and others. Certainly, the relationship between the perspectives was not lost on Williamson, as she notes in her 1998 article, but she notes a key difference between the two frameworks:

The (Ecological) Model differs from the Dervin’s Sense-Making Methodology which gives a central place to the “situation” resulting in a cognitive “gap.” Although the field work for present study also began with respondents’ “situations,” if they could be articulated, it also took into account the many variables which may influence the “situation,” or the type of information seeking or acquisition which may take place, even when a particular “situation” could not be described (Williamson, 1998, p. 35).

The Role of These Theories in This Study

In this study, Dervin’s Sense Making was seen as informing the methods (i.e., the interview protocol), while Williamson’s model supplied an ontology by which to classify observations. Dervin’s model (as shown in her famous stick-figure visualization) shows a process of encountering a situational gap and then actively seeking information to bridge this gap. Environmental factors are presumed to influence this process but are not explicitly defined. Williamson’s model, on the other hand, is explicit in naming the “what” and “where” of information acquisition, noting places in information ecology like personal networks and mass media, and factors that influence information experiences like values and socioeconomic status.

Williamson’s model supplies specific answers to questions that Dervin’s model provokes: what makes a bridge? What forms does a gap take? In this way, the models complement one another.

In Figure 1, we imagine Williamson’s model being stretched over Dervin’s. In doing this, Dervin’s model is not majorly altered. Simply, we are creating an ontology that allows us, as the researchers, to describe observed phenomena in a standardized way. We are able to envision information behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic as a process, but one that has clearly defined influences and boundaries, as uncovered in Williamson’s research with older adults. Ambiguities are avoided, as every part of the process has a clear set of possible attributes that can all be defined, as is shown in Table 1.

Figure 1. Visualization of Framework Used in this Study

Table 1 Definitions for All Attributes Examined in this Study

Type of Information Needed	Definition
Community	Information about events, activities, general updates (births, funerals) within the local community.
Everyday Life	Information sought to address a situation that emerges in everyday life (e.g., routine activities, hobbies).
Family	Information about family members’ well-being, activities, and general life updates (similar to community information, but specific to close family).

Financial	Information about financial affairs, both at micro (personal finance) and macro (stock market) levels.
Health	Information about one's health status or about specific health conditions and treatments (whether directly related to one's immediate health or not).
Political	Information about political events and activities, including legislative activities, elections, and politically-charged debates and discussions (e.g., masking-wearing during the COVID-19 pandemic).

Where Information was Found	Definition
Personal Network	Individuals with whom one regularly interacts: immediate family, friends, coworkers.
Wider Network	Individuals with whom one infrequently interacts or with whom one does not directly interact but interacts with someone in their personal network: Church members, friends of friends, coworkers of family.
Institutional Sources	Institutions with which one regularly interacts and which produce or disseminate information at an organizational level: government, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, corporate employer, research and policy publications.
Mass Media	Sources that broadly disseminate information to reach a large audience: television stations, radio programs, news/web publications, and certain social media (e.g., Twitter).

Influences	
Lifestyle	The way in which one lives, their pastimes, exercise, workplace situation, family relationships.
Personal Characteristics	Personality, mental and physical health, intellect.
Physical Environments	Area in which one lives, including both geographic and sociological influences on the individual.
Socioeconomic Circumstances	Personal wealth, wealth disparity, opportunity for social and economic mobility, housing security.
Values	Important beliefs that direct the way a person lives or thinks about issues that exist or arise in society.

Methods

Development of interview protocol

As noted in the prior section, the qualitative interview protocol for this study was informed by Dervin's (1998) Sense-Making Methodology. Nine questions, with a combined 14 sub-questions, were organized into four sections within the interview protocol, based on the categories of data we intended to collect: background information, situational factors that influence information seeking (lifestyles, physical environments, socioeconomic circumstances, values), types of needs or gaps (community, everyday life, family, financial, health, political, and where in the environment this information was found/bridging the need (personal network, wider network, institutional sources, mass media). The questions specifically targeted the types and sources of information that older adults have sought during the COVID-19 pandemic, how they settled on these sources, barriers to finding the information they need, incidents of unsuccessful information seeking, and how the pandemic has shifted their information ecology. The entire interview protocol is available as an appendix to this article.

The interview questions were pre-tested with feedback focusing on streamlining the protocol and reducing the length of interviews to avoid participant fatigue. Consequently, the interview protocol was finalized and submitted and received institutional review board (IRB) approval at the researchers' institution. Interviews were conducted in July and August of 2020.

As noted in the interview protocol, the following definitions were used in this study, and guide the analysis of this study's findings:

Information types are different types information you might look for on a special topic or for a special purpose , like information about politics (or a specific political

candidate), information about health issues (like the common cold), information about finances (like the stock market), etc.—for instance, “I use a lot of *financial information about the stock market*”

Information need is the specific information that you need at a point in time—for instance, “I *need information* about the *stock price for Walmart*”.

Information Seeking/Sought refers to the process of looking for information to address your information need—for instance, “Yesterday, I *sought information* about the *stock price for Walmart*”.

Information sources are any source of information used by a person, like your television, a newspaper, a book, other people, the Internet—for instance, “I *used the Internet* to seek information about the stock price for Walmart”.

This study’s coding scheme did not distinguish between online versus offline information sources (“mass media” includes television, print, and online news; “personal networks” includes face-to-face communication and Facebook chats or text messages). Nor did it distinguish whether certain information needs stated by participants directly referenced the COVID-19 pandemic. Information about a COVID-19 vaccine and information about surgical procedures during this period were both considered “health information,” because, despite variation, all of these information needs were impacted or related to the COVID-19 pandemic to some extent (e.g., surgical procedures/safety measures changed during the pandemic); this type of categorization also was not germane to the focus of the study, which was to examine information behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic, not necessarily information behavior *about* the COVID-19 pandemic.

Participants Characteristics

Older adults, defined as individuals age 65+, living in rural communities—defined, for the purposes of this study, as a town with a population of under 25,000 and located at least 30 miles from any city with a population above 100,000—within the state of Kansas (United States) were the research subjects in this study. The sampling for the interviews was a mixture of convenient (advertising for participants within rural communities near the researchers’ university) and stratified approaches, to ensure that a diversity of backgrounds (education, marital status/family size, urban/suburban/rural) were represented within the data. Table 2 displays the demographic composition of the sample set. None of the participants in this study were related to one another (i.e., only one member of a married couple was allowed to participate, to avoid biasing findings without overlapping responses).

Table 2. Demographics of Interview Participants

Table 1. Demographics of Interview Participants

Demographic Category	Frequency
Age	
65-70	10
71-75	11
76-80	5
81+	4
Gender Identity	
Female	11
Male	18
Not Specified/Nonbinary	1
Retirement Status	
Retired	17
Not Retired	8
Partial/Transition	5
Highest Level of Educational Attainment	
High School or Less	6
Some College	2
Associate’s Degree	3
Bachelor’s Degree	8
Graduate Degree	11

Relationship Status	
Single	5
In Relationship (Not Married)	1
Married	22
Widowed	2

Interview procedures

Given the circumstances surrounding the ongoing pandemic, participants were offered a variety of formats in which to complete the interview: via phone, Zoom video conferencing software, email, or in-person (assuming no other options were feasible and proper social distancing could be maintained). Eight of the participants opted for a phone interview, seven chose to use Zoom to facilitate the interview, 14 participated in an email interview, and one preferred an in-person interview. In all cases, participants were asked to first answer each question as fully as possible and then share any additional thoughts or feedback that they had. For email interviews, follow-up emails were used if needed to clarify responses that were unclear. There are limitations with each of these interview methods, particularly the lack of paralingual cues (tone, eye contact) with email interviews, but the researchers used follow-ups to help mitigate these limitations, which were difficult to avoid given the pandemic conditions.

Data analysis

Following each interview, responses were transcribed to a secure Microsoft Excel spreadsheet, with access restricted to the researchers. The resulting data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis. An analytical approach to content analysis was adapted from the work of Marshall and Rossman (2006):

- Both researchers read all the survey responses to get a sense of the responses; then they re-read the data marking all direct responses to the research questions;
- Responses were arranged into appropriate categories within the framework based on the definitions provided in the framework;
- From the survey responses, instances of verbatim narrative were selected to help illustrate alignment with the categories and emerging patterns in the data.

Intercoder reliability scores were calculated for the two coders, with a 96% level of agreement and a Cohen's Kappa of .92, indicating a very high level of agreement.

Findings

Types of information sought

As shown in Figure 2, the most named types of information that participants indicated they sought were health and political information. This was not particularly surprising, given that the COVID-19 pandemic and 2020 United States Presidential election weighed heavily on society as a whole and in the mind of the participants (older adults) in particular at the time of the study. As one participant stated, "I'm kind of in the vulnerable population, as they say, so keeping up-to-date on the COVID is something that I try to do lately." Political information was often also tied, to some extent, to the pandemic. As one participant noted, "I want to know how much (then-President) Trump is screwing things up." However, there were others who sought information about election polling, primary debates, and specific political organizations (e.g., "The Lincoln Project" and "Republican National Convention").

Participants were considerably less likely to report other types of information needs like family or financial, but many still did so. For instance, one participant discussed a family trip

that they had planned for over the summer—an “Alaskan cruise.” Given the state of the pandemic, the trip was cancelled by the cruise line, but customers were not given any instructions on how to receive a refund. The participant described several failed attempts at information seeking (web searching, asking family for assistance), before they finally decided to contact the travel company directly to get the information they needed. Contextually, the pandemic threw a lot of plans awry, creating situations (like the Alaskan cruise) where people were suddenly forced to search for information with only a limited understanding of where they could possibly go to find it.

Figure 2. Types of Information Sought

Compared to successfully sought information, there were few unsatisfied needs reported by participants. Among these, health was again the most prominent. The two unsatisfied health information needs that were most commonly reported related to the number of cases in a specific area (e.g., “what are the trends in the virus? How many people around here are dying?”) and the development of a vaccine (e.g., “I always keep an eye out for vaccine news”). Community

information—that which pertains to events in one’s immediate community or social environment—was the second-most common unsatisfied need. With community information, the need was related more to a desire to feel connected than a “need to know,” as one participant said, “(I) feel less connected to the community, the people who used to be a big part of my life.” It was common among respondents to substitute a need for information for a need for connectedness, a need to satisfy emptiness, loneliness, isolation. This was a context that likely always existed to some extent, but was exacerbated by the pandemic conditions, where participants were, “more isolated from friends and neighbors.”

Influences on information seeking

In Figure 3, the influences behind why participants sought the types and sources they did are classified based on the categories of contextual factors identified in Williamson’s (1996) research. Socioeconomic circumstances were noted very little, owing, in part, to the fact that all participants in the study were retired and, generally, of a middle-class, “well-off” economic status. Even when looking for financial information about stocks, participants were more likely to claim that they were motivated by “general worry” or anxiety, or concern for others, like their “children.” This was true of even participants who were of lower socioeconomic status. The concern was often far less about oneself. Those with higher educational attainment were more likely to name multiple motivations for seeking information and have novel motives like “intellectual curiosity” and “research to write a book.”

Figure 3. Influences on Seeking Information

Personal characteristics, including characteristics like anxiety/uncertainty, boredom, educational attainment (participants with greater attainment sought more information) were the most common influence. Physical environments, the second most-commonly identified motivation, is characterized by direct interactions with one's environment. During a non-COVID era, one's environment may be a greater influence on where information is sought; however, considering social distancing restrictions, one's environment was, in many cases, limited to one's home and the "interfaces" (computer, books, television) to which they had immediate access. Restrictions on mobility due to COVID restrictions were commonly cited among participants. One participant, whose comments were representative of about a dozen peers, mentioned, "though I did not leave my house too much before COVID, I really looked forward to going to the store, church, and such. It was one of my few opportunities to socialize with other people." Another participant noted that, "I am experiencing greater isolation now than ever before. I am now relying a lot on my family to share news of others (other people in the community)."

Some participants were also driven by the clash between personal characteristics (outgoing, need to communicate) and physical environments (social distancing) to find and use information primarily for social purposes. They may not have a personal information need but

may seize the opportunity to satisfy some communal need. For instance, one participant noted that a group of community members were looking for information about new residents in town: “(although) it wasn’t really important to me, I enjoyed helping to ask around on social media, because it gave me something to do and to catch up with some people I hadn’t spoken to in some time.”

Values and lifestyles, closely related motivations that develop early in life and rarely change across the life course, were both mentioned about a dozen times. Values (perhaps predictably) was a common motivation for seeking political information. One participant recounted the story of working to get a new political on the ballot ahead of the election in November. Though they understood that the party likely did not have much of a shot in the coming cycle, and there were risks to interacting with elections’ officials and collecting signatures from the public, a firm belief in the mission of the party drove them. This led them to seek (with varied levels of success) information about the political process from members of the local government and the community. Lifestyles were stronger motivations for source selection, with those who lead a less active lifestyle relying less on human or digital sources of information, preferring print or television. Comments by participants mentioned, “this is the convenient way (to find information)” and “it’s just what I do.”

Sources of information

Displayed in Figure 4 are the findings for sources of information reported by participants. Considerable differences existed in the information sources consulted by participants in successful and unsuccessful situations. While mass media and family and friends were the most-common sources for successful situations, other people (e.g., coworkers, community members) and institutional sources (e.g., government websites) were most common in unsuccessful

searches. The source that participants complained about the most was that of the Centers of Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), “it just feels like important things are missing. Maybe I just can’t find them on there, though.”

Figure 4. Sources of Information

Several participants made it clear that, “I CAN use the Internet,” but that they still like to use print and interpersonal (family and friend) sources if possible, even during the pandemic: “They are more familiar. I know how to get around them,” as one participant said. Other participants spoke proudly of their tech-savviness and how the pandemic had not significantly affected how they found information. As one participant noted, “I use my tablet. I can just open it up and all my news stories are there.” Emerging from these narratives about Internet use were three types of participants: those who expressed tech-savviness, those who express knowledge but not preference (the first group mentioned above), and those who expressed disinterest or opposition (rare among participants, but not absent). Internet use, in addition to serving its informational role, served a role in preserving social connectedness among some individuals.

Several participants remarked that they used Internet services like email and online social networking to connect with family, not necessarily for informational needs but just to “connect” and not “feel alone.”

Participants noted social media as a frequent information source. Generally, if a specific type of social media was provided by a participant, it was Facebook, though Twitter was also referenced on a few occasions. Participants expressed skepticism about health information shared on social media during the pandemic, but ultimately praised the convenience and quantity of information available: “They (social media sites) are the easiest and most convenient to use.” There were a few participants, however, who denounced these sites. One participant listed several specific websites (non-social media) and television stations they follow, “The New York Times and local papers, PBS, and I will listen to Fox News and NBC News sometimes just to get differing opinions on the topics.” Those who opposed social media and instead suggested a wide range of other sources that they used (four participants in total) all had an advanced education and were male. These individuals were also all married and considered family a source of information they could rely upon, perhaps mitigating the need to use social media for its social connectedness role.

Importantly, “success” was defined in this study based on the subjective judgement of the participants as to whether they found information that satisfied their need. “Success” was not attached to an objective measurement of information quality. So, it is feasible for a participant to read “fake news” and still believe that it successfully satisfied their need. In cases where participants deemed their search “unsuccessful,” it was due to either a complete lack of relevant information or the presentation of information that the participant either felt insufficient or unreliable. Given the mixed purposes for seeking information (not necessarily for explicitly

informative purposes but also to just connect with others), it is possible that success could also be defined on grounds besides actual satisfaction of information need.

Specific types of information sought from each source are shown in Table 3. Combining information types with the sources consulted, health information sought from mass media was the most common, followed by health information sought from family and friends. Social media was used commonly for seeking both political and health information (“It is the easiest to use”). Community information sought from “other people” was the most-common unsuccessfully sought type of information. The types and sources of information, to an extent, modulated the motivations for which the information was sought. For instance, health information sought from online social networking sites was commonly sought out of concern for others and was shared with others on the platform (by “sharing” a news post). Health information from mass media, particularly websites, was commonly sought out of concern for personal health. Political information on social media was often sought for the specific purpose of sharing it, not necessarily out of concern but more to make a value statement (“this is what I believe”) or try to convince others about a political point.

Table 3. Specific Types of Information Sought From Each Source

Table 2. Specific Types of Information Sought from Each Source

Type/Source of Information	Successfully Sought	Unsuccessfully Sought
Health Information from Mass Media	17	3
Health Information from Family/Friends	13	0
Political Information from Social Media	9	2
Health Information from Social Media	8	0
Family Information from Family/Friends	7	0
Health Information from Institutional Sources	6	3
Everyday Life Information from Mass Media	5	0
Political Information from Mass Media	4	0
Incidental Information from Social Media	3	0
Political Information from Family/Friends	3	0

Health Information from Other People (Not Family/Friends)	3	1
Incidental Information from Mass Media	2	0
Community Information from Other People	2	5
Political Information from a Book	1	0
Work Information from Other People	1	0
Financial Information from Institutional Sources	0	2
Political Information from Other People	0	1

Satisfaction of Information Needs

Whether information needs have been satisfied is a question of how “satisfaction” is defined. If satisfaction is taken as simply finding information that addresses the need, then needs were generally satisfied, other than for community information needs. This definition, however, does not consider whether the information was able to be acquired from the individual’s preferred source, nor does it attest to the validity/reliability of the information. Information was not always found via preferred sources. Pre-pandemic, many older adults preferred interpersonal sources of information, but during the pandemic mass media became their primary source of information. Relatedly, reliability of information can be called into question during the pandemic. Based on the specific sources of information named by some respondents (e.g., certain unreliable political news media), some types of information may be highly untrustworthy, by objective standards. Thus, it may not be appropriate to say that these individuals suffered from information poverty in an absolute sense (no information available whatsoever), but it would be appropriate to compare to other situations of information poverty like those described by Chatman (1996) in her work on the subject (information is limited, more difficult to find, and unreliable).

Discussion

General findings

In this study, participants indicated that the pandemic and upcoming election weighed heavily upon their minds during the year 2020. This information was not sought only for personal reasons, but also to share—with family and friends in order to connect socially and mitigate anxiety. The gaps these individuals faced were not purely informational. They were social and emotional as well. Based on this fact, it is not surprising to discover that, in order to bridge these gaps that they experienced, participants turned to social, interactive sources of information (direct interaction with family and friends, use of social media). Participants reported fewer barriers with these sources than when they used television shows or print resources to try to find information. However, there were also some instances where participants attempted to reach out to people beyond their immediate circle of family and friends and failed. In these cases where the search was unsuccessful, some participants would give up on searching, while others would look for the information in new places.

During the time in which this study was conducted, interaction with one's environment, and the people within it, was, generally, extremely limited by social distancing, closures, and other COVID mitigation measures. Many older adults—but certainly not all, especially given the skepticism towards COVID-19 displayed by some older adults in the Midwest United States – isolated from the public in order to avoid possibly contracting the virus. Several participants mentioned personal brushes with the virus: a case at their church or with a friend or family member, or a personal experience with contracting the disease. These events drove information seeking behavior, as the individual sought COVID-specific information to address their concerns about their own risk of contracting the virus, the symptoms, and the prognosis for their family and acquaintances.

Personal factors – including personality and health – were found to influence what behaviors were observed in the participants. Particularly, those who were more social, more educated, or in poorer health were more likely to isolate due to the pandemic and, consequently, feel more isolated and more restricted in their information sources. Environmental factors, particularly within the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, impacted why, how, and where information was sought. These findings align with those of a few similar studies conducted with other populations (younger adults, black women) during this period (Chandler et al., 2021; Lachlan et al., 2021). However, this study additionally shows that even information not related to the pandemic itself was impacted by the virus's presence during this period.

Theoretical implications

This study's findings reflect a convergence of social drives (finding information to share, seeking information as a means to maintain social connections) and the circumstances of physical separation. These two conditions have rarely before had to coexist. Even a very ill person could have family and friends visit with them at the hospital. Those who did isolate largely did so out of choice (not feeling the need to connect). However, in this context of the COVID-19 pandemic, individuals who would typically be engaged heavily within their community and with family and friends were isolated from their environment, placed in a bubble that is plagued by misinformation or a lack of information altogether, depending on the type of information being sought. This context is the exact opposite of those studied by Dervin and Williamson, who examined information rich community environments like assisted-living facilities.

Williamson's model identifies close interpersonal connections as the most immediate sources of information for older adults. While this, undoubtedly, would have been the preferred

source for many of the participants in this study under normal conditions (Heuberger & Ivanitskaya, 2011; Wilkins et al., 2018), the physical distancing barriers made in-person contact with family and friends an action that many considered selfish and shameful. Mass media and institutional sources were consulted more frequently, yet the objective still appeared to be a drive for interpersonal connections. Technology like online social networking was used because it allowed individuals to find information not just relevant to themselves but also to their families, and to share this information with their families directly on the same site. In this sense, the information worlds of the older adult still center around “family” and “community,” they just no longer rely on that communication to happen in the physical realm. The pandemic drove many of them online, where the concepts of personal networks and mass media are blended.

In finding information, a direct, personal information need was not all present. The “gap” identified by the individual might be better described a lack of social connection, while the “need” was more of an excuse to justify connecting with a source, which was itself not only a source of information but of that desired social connection (e.g., sharing a news story on social media) and associated interactivity. The “uses” of information could again be seen purely as tools to reach an end connecting with others. Sharing a news story that addresses a collective information need among family and friends (even if it was not so much a “need” for the individual) ensured that social connection was maintained (i.e., they were often driven by affective influences). This does not describe the information seeking of most participants in the study, but it is a theme that emerges from the data.

The single biggest deviation from the existing models of Dervin and Williamson in this study, though, was with wider personal networks—community members, coworkers, even social service professionals like librarians. These individuals, generally, are frequently consulted

because they are around and available. However, participants did not feel a strong need or ability to use them as a source of information during the pandemic. It was either not prudent or possible given the spread of the deadly disease. Thus, the “small worlds” of the individual got even smaller as personal networks dominated the lives of many of these individuals.

Practical Implications

There are a few practical implications to extrapolate from these findings. Mass media and close personal relationships played a major role as sources of information for these individuals during COVID-19, while wider network figures did not. However, wider network figures – community members, work acquaintances, and social services and libraries – are important sources of contradictory information (i.e., information that causes one to question their preconceived beliefs), whereas close family and friends and mass media are often sources of confirmation bias. This situation of the pandemic, then, may make some rural older adults more susceptible to misinformation and sustained misperceptions of reality. This elevates the need for concerned support agencies, like libraries, to provide (safe) outreach to these populations, perhaps arranging for community-wide online events facilitated through Zoom (with the library providing technical support) or socially-distanced activities.

It is also noteworthy that community information was difficult to find during this period. Communities are considered a common point of social connection for rural older adults and an absence of this community presence may increase social isolation and depression (Newman & Zainal, 2020; van Orden et al., 2020). Understanding the limitations to access to community during this period, and the sense of disconnection that can come with a poverty of community information, it may be seen as an imperative to find new ways to reach the older adult population in rural communities. It could also be beneficial to focus on the information sources to which

older adults do have access (family, mass media) as a way to build community as well, perhaps including highlighting local rural community news and people on the regional television news. Community newspapers and newsletter can provide some information, particularly if they are well written and provide diverse community perspectives. Family and friends who are still working in the community during a situation like the COVID-19 pandemic may be able to provide updates so that those older adults who are struggling with community exposure can retain better connections.

Limitations

There are several limitations to note for this study, in addition to opportunities for further research. Methodologically, using a qualitative, interview approach is useful for eliciting rich and less-forced data+ (as opposed to questionnaires that provide only discrete option choices). However, the energy exhausted to perform an interview-based study limits the number of participants in the study, limiting the generalizability of the findings. Future studies may utilize a mixed-methods approach (or base a questionnaire off the findings of this study) to expand the representativeness of the findings. Participants for this study were selected using a convenient sampling approach that focused on older adults in the area surrounding the researchers' university. This sampling approach, while not uncommon in qualitative research, does also limit the representativeness of the findings.

This study also focuses on a very specific period of time during the COVID-19 pandemic (late summer 2020). This was in the midst of the first real "peak" of the virus in the United States – and predated any major news about the development of a vaccine – so participants were likely more cautious than they would be in later stages of the virus progression when their understanding of the virus was more-advanced. The context of rural Kansas may also limit the

generalizability of some of the findings, as we know that rural older Kansans tend to be very conservative politically (Kansas's 1st Congressional District, for instance, is one of the most consistently conservative in the nation), which, in the United States, was correlated with greater skepticism towards the virus and the necessity for preventative measures (though many older conservatives did take their own preventative measures even if they thought it was unnecessary for their younger, healthy relatives to do so) (Latkin et al., 2021).

Conclusion

Though the COVID-19 pandemic led many older adults to physically isolate, the drive to connect socially with other people and to ensure the health and well-being of family and friends did not diminish. As the information environments of these individuals changed, they continued to see close personal connections as a way to seek information as well as feel less isolated in their homes. Unsurprisingly, information about the virus itself was the most sought-after, followed by political information (influenced by the upcoming 2020 election). However, the motivations for seeking this information were more complex. Navigating shifting circumstances in source availability led to behaviors that were markedly distinct from those that may have been expected in the pre-pandemic era. A myriad of affective influences (i.e., the social drive to connect with others) combined with uncertainty about the evolving COVID situation, led this vulnerable population of older adults to turn to collaborative platforms like online social networking sites to seek information during this crisis period of the peak COVID-19 pandemic.

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Appendix

Interview Protocol

Definitions:

Note for the study participants:

- **Information types** are different types information you might look for on a special topic or for a special purpose, like information about politics (or a specific political candidate), information about health issues (like the common cold), information about finances (like the stock market), etc.—for instance, “I use a lot of financial information about the stock market”
- **Information need** is the specific information that you need at a point in time – for instance, “I need information about the stock price for Walmart”
- **Information Seeking/Sought** refers to the process of looking for information to address your information need – for instance, “Yesterday, I sought information about the stock price for Walmart”
- **Information sources** are any source of information used by a person, like your television, a newspaper, a book, other people, the Internet—for instance, “I used the Internet to seek information about the stock price for Walmart”

Background Information:

1. What is your age?
2. Are you retired/how long?
3. What was your highest level of educational attainment?
4. What is your current living situation like?
5. Has the COVID-19 pandemic caused any major difficulties in your life?

6. Is there anything special about yourself that you would like to share?

Section 1:

7. Think about situations during the COVID-19 pandemic where you needed information to answer a question or solve a problem.

Questions:

- a. What types of information have you sought?
 - (e.g., “information about the local cases of coronavirus”)
- b. What led you to seek these types of information?
 - (e.g., “I was concerned about how many cases there were locally”)
- c. What sources did you use to find this information?
 - (e.g., “Center for Disease Control’s website”)
- d. What led you use these sources as opposed to others?
 - (e.g., “I knew how to find them and wasn’t sure about other sources”)
- e. What adjustments did you have to make when seeking out this information?
 - (e.g., “I would normally ask my doctor for medical information help, but he wasn’t easy to get ahold of”)

Section 2:

8. Think about a time recently during the COVID-19 pandemic where you looked for information to answer a question or solve a problem but were not able to find the information you wanted.
 - a. What were the types of information that you sought but could not or had difficulty finding?
 - (e.g., “information about when I would receive a stimulus check”)

- b. What sources did you use to seek this information?
 - (e.g., “in the local newspaper”)
 - c. What were the sources of information that you sought/would have used but could not find?
 - (e.g., “I probably would have asked my accountant, but I couldn’t find her phone number and her office was closed)
 - d. What was your response to this lack of information that you needed?
 - (e.g., “I stopped looking and tried to forget about it”)
 - **Section 3:**
9. Think about recent times during the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic where you looked for information to answer a question or solve a problem and were able to successfully find and use the information you wanted.
- a. What types of information that you found were useful?
 - (e.g., “information about a political candidate”)
 - b. What led you to seek this type of information?
 - (e.g., “I was interested in the candidate’s background”)
 - c. What sources of information were helpful for what you needed?
 - (e.g., “I Googled it”)
 - d. What led you to use this particular source to seek this information?
 - (e.g., “I was familiar and comfortable with it”)
 - e. What made these experiences different from those where you were not able to find the information you needed?
 - (e.g., “I knew where to find this type of information”)

Additional Comments:

- a. Do you have any additional comments about how recent world events have impacted the information you seek and use and from where you seek it?
- b. Do you have any additional comments about the overall design of this study or interview questions?